

LINGUISTIC DISORDERS FOUND IN CHILD SPEECH

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Annotation: *Speech development devices are at the junction of many specialties. The speech function is key for the development of a child's thinking and intelligence in general, therefore, a violation of speech formation inevitably entails a lag in the development of thinking, a violation of communication and socialization, the occurrence of behavioral disorders and school failure.*

Keywords: *speech pathologists, intellectual development, language sphere*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada bola nuqtida uchraydigan lingvistik buzilishlar haqida soʻz boradi. Nutq funktsiyasi umuman bolaning tafakkuri va aql-idrokini rivojlantirish uchun kalit hisoblanadi, shuning uchun nutqni shakllantirishning buzilishi muqarrar ravishda fikrlash rivojlanishining kechikishiga, aloqa va ijtimoiylashuvning buzilishiga, xulq-atvor buzilishlarining paydo bo'lishiga va maktabdagi muvaffaqiyatsizlikka olib keladi.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *nutq patologlari, intellektual rivojlanish, til sohasi*

Speech development disorders can be observed in a wide range of diseases that occur in general pediatric practice. So, their cause may be chronic otitis media and other conditions leading to hearing impairment, epilepsy and convulsive epileptic encephalopathy, abnormalities in the development of the articulatory apparatus, cerebral palsy and many other conditions.

Classifications of speech development disorders

Pediatricians, neurologists, psychiatrists, otorhinolaryngologists, sign language therapists, psychologists, speech pathologists are engaged in the study of this

pathology. This causes a difference in approaches to understanding and classifying speech disorders and the complexity of interdisciplinary interaction of specialists.

Non-medical specialists (speech therapists, speech pathologists, psychologists) use

classifications based on qualitative and quantitative characteristics of speech disorders, and by doctors - based on etiological and pathogenetic mechanisms and nosological affiliation.

In the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision, primary speech disorders are divided under the heading "disorders of psychological (mental) development" and are divided into the following:

- 1) specific speech articulation disorder,
- 2) expressive speech disorder,
- 3) receptive speech disorder,
- 4) acquired aphasia with epilepsy (Landau-Kleffner syndrome),
- 5) other speech and language development disorders.

ICD-10, as well as B8M-5, takes speech development disorders beyond the limits of general intelligence, emphasizing in diagnostic criteria that in order to diagnose, for example, a receptive speech disorder, intellectual development must comply with the norm. Nevertheless, it seems unlikely that the intellectual development of a 3-4-year-old child who does not understand the addressed speech will correspond to the norm. Moreover, the use of standardized methods to determine the level of intelligence in such children often turns out to be impossible. In many foreign sources, one can find an explanation that only the level of nonverbal intelligence should be taken into account. Nevertheless, according to one of the widely used English-language manuals on child psychiatry, many children with delayed speech development demonstrate low indicators of nonverbal intelligence, but cannot be diagnosed as mentally retarded. At the same time, in children with ZPR, speech development may proceed normally or with minor deviations. It is

obvious that the presence of speech syndromes in the structure of the SPD will significantly aggravate the severity of the condition and interfere with adaptation.

Moreover, this condition cannot be explained by organic brain damage, intellectual insufficiency, hearing impairment or structural features of the articulatory apparatus. The delay in the formation of neuronal connections of speech regions of the brain is considered as the reason. The frequent occurrence of similar disorders in relatives also suggests the genetic basis of this disorder. As a rule, children suffering from dyslalia do not have other violations of the language sphere - they demonstrate the presence of a sufficient passive and active vocabulary, a level of understanding of reversed speech for their age. A specific disorder of speech articulation occurs in approximately 10% of children under the age of 8 years and in 5% of children older than 8 years. As a rule, correction involves systematic classes with a speech therapist.

The utterance of the first words is sharply delayed (2-3 years), phrases either do not appear at all, or arise in a very simplified form at the age of 5-6. In general, all aspects of speech (pronunciation, lexical and grammatical) are violated. A child with motor alalia is characterized by extremely low speech activity, sound pronunciation and phrasal speech suffer the most, and the possibilities of mastering the norms of the native language are persistently violated. But along with this, even preschoolers are inquisitive, interested in what is happening around them, trying to occupy themselves. They are capable of the simplest generalizations, cope with many non-verbal tasks.

Thus, with sensorimotor alalia, there is no understanding of speech, and its expressive function suffers a second time. Children with sensorimotor alalia with preserved hearing have a clear misunderstanding of speech - "closure acupathy", and some suffer more auditory attention, while others have the ability to differentiate phonemes and words. A child with sensorimotor alalia has disorders of voluntary attention due to the exhaustion of auditory function; children do not know how to

"listen", get tired quickly, lose interest. Often the child comes into contact only with close people, which is due to such features in communication as pronounced intonation coloration, gestural accompaniment of the mother's speech. The selectivity of the reaction to the change in the pitch of the speaker's voice is characteristic. At the stage of increasing speech activity, acquiring the character of communication, manifestations of echolalia become pronounced. At the same time, a child with sensory can participate in outdoor games with peers that do not require verbalization. Children can demonstrate very good constructive abilities, cope well with mathematical tasks, and are completely unsuccessful in those areas where sufficient development of verbal intelligence is required. Most often, such patients are diagnosed with mental retardation at medical and pedagogical commissions, despite the high figures of nonverbal intelligence. However, such children cannot even master the program of the correctional class, since in this case a completely different approach to learning is necessary for successful assimilation of the material.

Other disorders of speech and language development. In the USA and Australia, another term is widely used in relation to receptive speech disorders - auditory processing disorder. It combines a variety of conditions in which there is a violation of the processing of audio stimuli by the cerebral cortex with preserved hearing. According to the American Speech, Language and Hearing Association, this disorder is manifested by a violation in one or more functions:

1. The ability to localize the sound source in space.
2. The ability to distinguish individual sounds from a variety of sounding ones.
3. The ability to recognize similarities and differences between sounds.
4. The ability to recognize a sequence of sounds, integrate this sequence into words and perceive stimuli separately when they quickly follow each other.
5. The ability to recognize speech or other sounds against the background of a competing audio stimulus.

6. The ability to recognize an audio stimulus even if it is changed or shortened.

Based on the clinical description, the disorder of processing classroom information in children corresponds to the more widely used in European countries impressive speech disorder and the sensory alalia syndrome described earlier by Soviet psychiatrists. However, it should be noted that unlike the USA and European countries, in Russia there is a decline in interest in speech disorders in children from psychiatrists. Some patients with sensorimotor alalia syndrome are diagnosed within the framework of autism spectrum disorders, since it is often possible to observe the similarity of individual symptoms. It may also be because the intellectual development of such patients cannot be called normal, which contradicts the criteria of ICD-10.

Depending on the social context, complex and non-standard grammatical constructions. There is an inability to ask relevant questions, to adapt statements to the reaction of the interlocutor. It also describes such a feature as the inability to lie and cheat, most likely related to the inability to understand the purpose of deception. These violations inevitably lead to restrictions in social interaction and adaptation. In this regard, the affiliation of this condition to autism spectrum disorders is widely discussed in the literature. According to D.V.M. Bishop, this term may be useful to refer to patients who do not fully meet the criteria of autistic disorder, but whose speech disorders lead to pronounced violations of social interaction and contact.

Thus, speech development disorders in children can be a symptom of a wide variety of conditions. Identification of the etiology and pathogenetic mechanisms of speech disorders is an important task of a doctor of any specialty and is necessary to determine the further tactics of treatment of the patient. The difference in approaches to understanding speech disorders in the domestic and foreign literature and the lack of a single generally accepted classification complicates the timely identification and treatment of these conditions. It would be necessary to develop a general

classification that combines both medical and psychological and pedagogical aspects of these disorders.

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